

THE INTEGRATED SKILLS DEVELOPMENT PLANNING MODEL (ISDPM) IN MENTORING

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Abstract:

The paper highlights the Integrated Skills Development Planning Model (ISDPM) detailing the dimensions of model (phases and locus of control) and the possible uses, particularly in higher education and pedagogical practicum. The model is approached from the perspective of mentoring and coaching, in the context of other mentoring models presented in the international literature (Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development, Biggs's Presage-Process-Product Model, GROW, Megginson and Clutterbuck's mentoring process model etc.). Several directions and future research are also formulated in order to clarify several important issues concerning the use of the model in higher education.

Keywords: mentoring, coaching, mentoring models, The Integrated Skills Development Planning Model, ISDPM.

1. Current approaches on mentoring

The concept of mentoring originates from the Homer's epic poem, *The Odyssey*, in which Odysseus, the King of Ithaca entrusts one of his most loyal friends, Mentor, the mission to teach and counsel his son, Telemachus. Even from the beginning, mentoring was closely related to the activity of giving someone good advice, being a model, helping an individual to reach his or her full potential.

In a previous study, we highlighted several definitions of mentoring in the international and national literature (Strunga and Martin, 2000):

- Support, assistance, advocacy or guidance given by one person to another in order to achieve an objective or several objectives over a period of time (SOVA)
- One-to-one, non-judgemental relationship in which an individual voluntarily gives time to support and encourage another. This is typically developed at a time of transition in the mentee's life, and lasts for a significant and sustained period of time (Active Community Unit, Home Office)
- The support of one individual by another within a personal relationship developed through regular contact over a period of time (Pan London Standard)

Other authors consider that mentoring is a process involving two or more individuals working together to develop the abilities of one individual. The context of the mentoring relationship can focus on career and/or personal

development (Bryant-Shanklin, 2022). In the recent years, the concept of mentoring was expanded to include relationships that extend beyond the immediate parameters of the university (Goodyear, 2009 apud Bryant-Shanklin, 2022) and the integration of the new information and communication technologies, giving rise to a series of new mentoring and coaching models.

2. Perspectives on mentoring models

The mentoring model represents a complex framework for the professionalization of human resources, framed in a system of professional, ethical and human values, in which the mentor-disciple relationship is expressed at the highest standards of quality and performance, resulting in the formation of a new professional in a field of activity.

In relation to the particularities of the mentoring process, Stan (2020) distinguishes three mentoring models:

- *Apprentice mentorship model* - representing the direction of the disciple's training activity, by an experienced mentor, who provides support and development direction, based on systematic observations of the disciple's activity.
- *Competency-based model* - is based on the expertise of the mentor, who can transfer his skills to the disciple, naturally, with the skill and ease characteristic of a professional with high expertise in a field of activity.
- *The reflexive model* - considers the development of the disciple's metacognitive capacities, through methods of introspection such as: self-analysis, self-knowledge, self-conviction or self-discipline. This is a modern model, which is based on the application of professional counseling and coaching (mental training) techniques, which lead to the professionalization of the disciple to high standards.

We believe that, in relation to various criteria (the relationship established between the mentor and the disciple; the venue: on site or online; the duration of the mentoring process; the structure of the process and the strategies used) a multitude of models can be configured, which can reflect more or less accurately the quality of the results obtained. In this sense, we also propose a possible mentoring model, with the value of analysis and reflection, which we will later test experimentally in subsequent longitudinal research at the level of Romanian higher education.

In her excellent study, Kamarudin et al analyze three main mentoring models, relevant to the topic of our study (Kamarudin et al, 2020): a) the zone of proximal development (ZPD) and scaffolding model proposed by Lev Vygotsky in the context of the sociocultural theory of learning; b) Biggs's Presage-Process-Product Model, that highlights the processual nature of mentoring and coaching and the GROW model, advanced by Alan Fine, Graham Alexander and Sir John Whitmore, that describes the four mentoring phases: a) goals (formulating realistic and operational objectives); reality (understanding the current situation and taking account of all the factors and variables involved in the decision-making process); options (analyzing the different options that the individual has in a specific context) and d) way forward (choosing a specific option and following its consequences for the mentee and organization).

Megginson and Clutterbuck have a different approach, constructing a model based on detailed mentoring phases, such as: (a) Establishing and managing the counseling and mentoring relationship; (b) Establishing specific objectives; (c) Clarification and understanding of situations; (d) Facilitating the process of self-knowledge; (d) Understanding the behavior of other people; (e) Overcoming obstacles; (f) Stimulation of creative thinking; (g) Decision-making; (h) Taking action; (i) Managing the client's own behaviors; (j) Building wider

networks of support, influence and learning; (k) Review and Termination of Counseling or Mentoring Relationship. The last phase could be supplemented by adding another one consisting of developing personal strategies and methods (Megginson and Clutterbuck, 2005).

3. The Integrated Skills Development Planning Model (ISDPM)

ISDPM (Integrated Skills Development Planning Model) could be a solution that could facilitate discussion and reflection on mentoring, and it is based on three main levels (see Table 1 below): (1) Identifying the competences and skills to which the client aspires; (2) Analyzing the gap between current skills and desired / needed skills; (3) Formulating an action plan towards achieving the desired skills. ISDPM was structured on two main dimensions: (a) the mentoring process dimension, from the perspective of the mentee: identification, analysis and planning respectively (b) the locus of control dimension (external and internal). Each combination of the two dimensions gives us a particular set of tasks for the mentoring team, which includes the mentor and mentee(s):

- (1) *External Identification* is related to finding out what are the skills that are necessary to successfully fill a position or efficiently achieve the tasks for the current job position; in this specific phase, both mentor and mentee analyze the job description, the necessary competences for a certain job, what are the main responsibilities related to the job, what are requested qualifications.
- (2) *Internal Identification* requires a deep reflection on the skills the mentee have in relation to the job position; it is advisable to start from the qualifications of the mentee right to the real competences he or she has in

that specific field of work and regarding the job position that is discussed in the mentoring sessions.

- (3) *External Analysis* is focused on highlighting the gap between the requested skills and the skills that are necessary for the job position. It is important to note that sometimes the requested skills (formulated in the job description) are not always identical to the skills that are necessary because the concrete reality is very complex and dynamic hence the necessary skills are similar to a moving target that is not always updated in the job description.
- (4) *Internal Analysis* is focused on the gap between the requested skills and the skills that the mentee currently has. An additional layer of analysis could be done on the gap between the necessary skills and the skills that the mentee currently has. Mentoring process could really help an individual to better understand the gap using specific methods and techniques applied to specific job tasks and responsibilities.
- (5) *External Planning* can have a very important role on the overall mentoring process if the management team of the institution / organization is involved in the mentoring process. On the one side, the mentee could reflect which resources he or she can use to fulfill the job tasks, which is the level on institutional support that is needed, if the necessary resources are available. On the other side, the mentor could direct the mentee to access the institutional resources and act as a facilitator to different channels, networks and resource pools for the particular activities related to the job. The management team could have an important role in directing the institutional resources toward the places they are needed in the mentoring process. Hence, the mentor is acting as an intermediary between the management team and the mentee.

(6) *Internal planning* is concerned with formulating a concrete plan on how to reduce the gap between the requested / necessary skills and the skills that the mentee has at a certain moment. This phase is related to the operational and methodological aspects of the mentoring process, viewed from the perspective of the self-management of learning. These activities are also closely related to the metacognitive competences that help in regulating the mentee’s behavior to both the internal and external learning situations. The concrete plan could start from an individual reflection on several specific job tasks and situations and in the second phase, could be discussed with the mentor in several sessions. It is very important that, after several weeks or months, to review the action plan in order to change or improve the suggested activities and indicators. The plan should include concrete steps that are simple and easy to observe and assess.

	<i>Identification</i>	<i>Analysis</i>	<i>Planning</i>
<i>External</i>	What skills are necessary?	The gap between the requested skills and those that are necessary	How can the organization support me?
<i>Internal</i>	What skills do I have?	The gap between the requested skills and the skills that I have	What is my plan to reduce the gap?

Table 1. The Integrated Skills Development Planning Model (ISDPM) in mentoring

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

In this paper we have presented a new mentoring model that could have several benefits for mentoring and coaching activities. First, the ISDPM is more flexible in the sense that can be used in a variety of mentoring situations and contexts and for both mentoring and coaching. Second, the model is dynamic meaning that facilitates action and change from the identification of the issues, understanding the gaps and planning towards reaching the goals. Third, the model has a holistic approach to the mentoring, which is viewed from multiple perspectives, internal and external. Many mentoring models have a limited scope because they are exclusively focused on either one of these dimensions. The ISDPM was initially designed to be used in educational setting (particularly in higher education) but it is very easy to adapt it in different contexts such as a business environment.

However, more studies are needed in order to better understand the impact this model has on the performance of the mentees. Several research directions could be highlighted such as: How is the model related to the level of metacognitive competences? What is the impact of the model on educational performances and results? What are the perceptions of the mentees and mentors on the utility, accessibility and efficiency of the model? How can the model be integrated in educational activities such as pedagogical practicum.

In conclusion, ISDPM could be a valuable tool in both mentoring and coaching, if used in conjunction with many other mentoring tools and techniques, and in the context of a more general mentoring strategy in which all the stakeholders are included, particularly the management team, colleagues, business associated, etc.

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